

SORPTION OF COBALT (II) AND NICKEL (II) IONS FROM INDUSTRIAL WASTEWATER ONTO MODIFIED BENTONITE CLAYS

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Abstract. *In this study, the chemical-mineralogical composition, physico-chemical properties of bentonite clay of Shafirkon mine were studied. Methods of modification of bentonite clay of Shafirkon mine were developed. The sorption isotherm of the sorption of cobalt (II) and nickel (II) ions contained in industrial wastewater to modified bentonite clays was determined based on physical and chemical laws. The thermodynamics of the regeneration process of adsorbents of modified Shofirkon mine bentonite clay was scientifically substantiated. Based on the obtained experimental data, the modified Shofirkon mine bentonite clay was used to solve environmental problems, i.e., the scientific basis for the rational use of limited water resources was created by cleaning the waste water of enterprises.*

Introduction. Today, the rapid development of industry in the world causes an increase in the demand for sorbents with high sorption properties for wastewater treatment, water treatment and demineralization in enterprises. In particular, the use of sorbents based on cheap and convenient raw materials for the purification of wastewater from heavy metal ions in industrial enterprises is largely supported by modern advances in science and technology. Earth's water resources play a very important role at the current stage of development of society and production as the main natural energy carrier, raw material, cleaning agent, etc. It is important to introduce modern water supply systems that save water to production and technological processes, to create new high-efficiency tools and to improve existing technologies of industrial wastewater treatment, to introduce significant new approaches to solving current technical problems.

Today, in the world, there is a need to study the processes of cleaning industrial wastewater generated during the technological processes of raw materials processing and product production, to develop optimal technological developments based on the results of comprehensive research on the search for new available sorbents and natural resources. Special attention is paid to scientific research on effective treatment of wastewater from pollutants and related components and elimination of existing problems in the field.

Experiment and its analysis. Based on the criteria for determining the sorption reactions of cobalt (II) and their direct influence on the degree of sorption to bentonite, for example, the composition and concentration of the saline environment, the influence of pH of the environment, etc., a comprehensive study. . not done before. When interacting with NH_3 and Co^{2+} in amounts up to 1.08 mol/l, complex compounds are formed in the form of hydrocomplexes:

Based on the results of Cotton's research, active Co^{2+} ions in the form of $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ can have an octahedral shape and $\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^{2+}$ can have a partial tetrahedral shape. They maintain a state of mutual balance. Presumably, this situation is observed when Co^{2+} ammonia is formed. Taking this situation into account, we studied the effect of pH in the presence of NH_3 and NO_3^- anions for the co-precipitation of Co^{2+} with concentrations up to 4.5×10^{-4} mol / l.

During co-precipitation, Co^{2+} is a solution of potassium nitrate, ammonium, sodium carbonate, ammonium chloride, and nitric acid (NH_4NO_2) in the background of the salt, and different methods were used to mix the reagents:

- 1) co-precipitation: as a carrier — 1.25 g bentonite Co^{2+} extracted from an acidic medium;
- 2) sorption: cobalt salt was added to bentonite;
- 3) precipitation: under similar conditions, the loss of Co^{2+} is the precipitation of its solid phase.

The amount of sorption was determined by the radioactivity indicator using cobalt isotopes ^{57}Co and ^{58}Co , in which the contact time of the sediment with the solution was 30 minutes; other parameters of the experiment and their methodology literature.

Figure 1. Graph of state and sorption of Co^{2+} in 1M potassium nitrate
1 and 2 — fractions of Co^{2+} and $\text{Co}_4(\text{OH})_4^{4+}$ ions, respectively;
3 and 4 — deposition of $\text{Co}(\text{II})$ hydroxide, respectively

As can be seen from Figure 1. Sorption of Co^{2+} in bentonite clays in 1 M KNO_3 begins at $\text{pH} = 5$, which corresponds to the beginning of Co^{2+} hydrolysis ($\text{pH} 8.3 \div 9$). The concentration of Co^{2+} in the specified sorption parameters is allowed, then it is separated from the carrier, as well as the precipitation of the carrier at $\text{pH} = 5$ or the injection of the solution obtained by dissolving the microcomponent in a minimum amount of acid. high concentration NH_3 solution. During sorption, two maxima of precipitation in the presence of $\text{Co}^{2+} \text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3$ are observed: $\text{pH} = 7.0 \div 7.5$ and $\text{pH} = 10.0$. As the concentration of ammonium nitrate increases from 1 to 3 mol, deposition decreases in the range $\text{pH} = 7 \div 10$, and therefore sorption. Co^{2+} decreases to $b > 3$ mol ammonium nitrate at $\text{pH} = 8.0$.

At the same time, it can be seen from Figure 2 that with increasing salt concentration, age-dependent sorption is observed at $\text{pH} = 7.0$, that is, in the region of cobalt (II) hydrolysis, which is confirmed by the data presented.

In order to establish the process and the mechanism of separation of Ni from other elements, the concentration of Ni^{2+} during its separation in wastewater with precipitation by metal hydroxides was studied.

Figure 2. Graph of state and sorption of Co^{2+} in 1M ammonium nitrate.

1-7 – ion fractions $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2^{2+}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3^{2+}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4^{2+}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{2+}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_3^-$; 8 - sorption $2,5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ g-ion/l Co^{2+} in 1 M NH_4NO_3 , 9 - the same, in 1 M KNO_3

Ni^{2+} ions are considered to cause hydrolysis reactions with the formation of the following hydroxy cations:

a) $\text{NiOH}^{\cdot}$ ($\lg K_1=5,0$; K_1 – hydrolysis constant);

b) $\text{Ni}_2(\text{OH})^{3+}$ ($\lg \beta_{1,2}=9,0$);

c) $\text{Ni}_4(\text{OH})_4^{4+}$ ($\lg \beta_{4,4}=27,82$)

The first hydroxy compound precipitates at $\text{Ni}_2(\text{OH})_2$ pH=8.0, where, according to the authors, it is: 13.81; 14.5; 15.21; 18.06 and 17.19.

In the presence of ammonia with a concentration higher than 1.08 mol/l, nickel (II) forms amino acids ($\lg$ formation constants are shown in parentheses).

$\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)^{2+}(2,80)$; $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_2^{2+}(5,04)$; $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_3^{2+}(6,77)$; $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_4^{2+}(7,96)$; $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_5^{2+}(8,71)$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{2+}(8,74)$.

In the continuation of the experiments, the sorption of nickel (II) was studied in the presence of ammonia, Cl^- , CO_3^{2-} , ClO_4^- and NO_3^- depending on the change of pH of the medium. ions in solution, at different concentrations of sorbed component and ambient electrolyte, in bentonite clays. In this case, solutions of KNO_3 , NaClO_4 , NH_4NO_3 and KNO_3 , K_2CO_3 were used as saline medium. Under these experimental conditions, the order of substitution of reagents was modified as follows:

- 1) co-precipitation: 1.25 g of sample bentonite as a carrier was separated from the acidic medium together with the sorbed component;
- 2) sorption: the sorbed component was added to bentonite sediment;
- 3) sedimentation: under similar conditions, loss of nickel due to sedimentation of its solid phase, absorption by vessel walls, etc.

Based on the amount of nickel in the centrifuge, the sedimentation index was determined using the photometric method using dimethylglyoxime, the contact time of the sediment with the solution was 20 minutes, other parameters remained unchanged.

The amount of precipitation was determined photometrically using dimethylglyoxime from the amount of nickel in the centrifuge; contact time of the precipitate with the solution is 20 minutes. Other conditions were as described above.

Sorption of $4,5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ g-ion/l nickel in 1 m KNO_3 starts at pH =5 and is completed in the range of pH =7.5-10. In such conditions, it is possible to concentrate nickel, which is then separated from the carrier by precipitation, the latter at pH = 5, or by injecting a concentrated ammonia solution into bentonite clay sediment, followed by desorption on the nickel surface. sediment.

**Figure 3. Curves of nickel(II) precipitation in bentonite clay
1 mol NaClO₄ and 1 mol, 2.5 mol, 4 mol NH₄NO₃
Co-precipitation, sorption and precipitation in 1mol NaClO₄;
4-6 — the same, 1 mol NH₄NO₃, 7-9 — the same, 2.5 mol NH₄NO₃,
10-12 — the same, in 1 mol of NH₄NO₃.**

Sorption of nickel in 1 mol KNO₃, 1 mol NaClO₄ and 1 mol KNO₃ +0.5 mol K₂CO₃ is almost the same. At 1 mol of NH₄NO₃, the maximum co-precipitation is observed at pH > 7.9 (Fig. 3). When the concentration of NH₄NO₃ increases to 5 M, co-precipitation and sorption decrease in the regions. pH = 8.9-10, as well as its magnitude and the position of the first maximum on the rN axis. As the alkalinity of the solution increases, the sorption of nickel drops to zero in the range of pH = 8.9-10 in a 2.5 NH₄NO₃ solution (Fig. 3).

Conclusion. The research results can also be explained by the sequential occurrence of the following reactions: in a weakly acidic environment with pH =5, the reaction of hydrolysis of Ni²⁺ ions mainly begins with the formation of Ni₄(OH)₄⁴⁺ ions, which changes the ratio of hydrolyzed forms with increasing rN of the environment corresponds to the data calculated on At the same time, the fractional fractions of NiOH⁺ and Ni₂OH³⁺ are insignificant compared to the fraction of tetramer Ni(OH)₄⁴⁺ (Fig. 3.6).

Thus, the nickel sorption process in bentonite starts with the appearance of Ni(OH)₄²⁺ in the solution and does not occur if only aquilones are present in the solution.

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